

Morpholine-4-Carbodithioate as an Analytical Reagent for Gravimetric Determination of Copper(II)

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Copper (II) has been precipitated quantitatively with morpholine-4-carbodithioate over the pH range 3.0-11.0. The sensitivity of the reagent is 6.0 $\mu\text{g.}$ for copper (II). The separation and determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) has been made in their binary mixtures using ammoniacal solution of EDTA and tartarate. The separation of copper(II) from cobalt(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Sn(II), Mg(II), Ga(III), In(III), Al(III), Th(IV) and U(VI) is made possible by using an ammoniacal mixture of EDTA and tartarate as the masking agent. Oxo-titanium(IV) and oxo-vanadium(IV) are masked with sodium flouride. The anions, viz. Br^- , F^- , CH_3COO^- , CNS^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} , BO_3^{3-} , citrate and tartarate do not interfere in the determination of copper(II), whereas thiosulphate interferes.

Although Bayer and Ott¹ reported morpholine-4-carbodithioate as a possible analytical reagent, the survey of the literature reveals that no analytical work has been carried out on this reagent. In the present communication morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been used as an analytical reagent for the quantitative separation and determination of Cu(II) and Ni(II).

Experimental

Potassium salt of the reagent was prepared according to the procedure given by Macrotrigiano, *et. al.*² The potassium morpholine dithiocarbamate has been prepared by treating morpholine in dry ether with carbon-disulphide and adding potassium hydroxide during four hours, under vigorous stirring. (Molar ratios, morpholine : carbon-disulphide : KOH = 1 : 1 : 1). The crude product was recrystallised from isopropyl-alcohol (melting point of the acid = 175°).

Procedure for the Determination of Copper(II) :

Aliquots (containing 3.5-100 mg.) of the standard solution of the copper (II) were diluted to about 150 ml. with distilled water and the pH was adjusted in between 3.0 and 7.5, by adding appropriate quantities of the acetate buffer solution. A 1% (w/v) solution of the KMDTC in distilled water was then added with constant stirring. A brown precipitate gradually separated out which was digested on a water-bath (60-75°) for about 30-40 minutes. The precipitate was filtered off in a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed with distilled water several times. It was then dried at 110-120° for two hours and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_2$. The results of the estimations of copper(II) are given in Table 1.

Sl. No.	Cu(II) mg	Complex mg	Cu(II) Found mg	% Error
1	12.63	77.2	12.64	+0.07
2	18.95	115.6	18.92	-0.16
3	25.26	154.4	25.27	+0.11
4	31.58	192.8	31.56	-0.06
5	50.52	308.2	50.45	-0.13

Effect of foreign ions :

Determination of copper (II) was carried out in the presence of anions and cations. The anions, viz. Br^- , F^- , CNS^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, BO_3^{3-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, tartarate, citrate and EDTA in three fold excess did not interfere in the determination of copper(II). Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Sn(II), Mg(II), Al(III), In(III), Ga(III), Th(IV) and U(VI) did not interfere in the presence of an ammoniacal mixture of 0.1M tartarate and 0.1M EDTA. Oxo-titanium(IV) and oxo-vanadium(IV) were masked by adding sodium flouride. In the determination of copper(II) in the presence of the above mentioned ions, masking agents were added prior to the addition of the reagent ; the mixture gently heated, and the pH was adjusted to 5.0-7.5 with acetate buffer.

Seapration and Determination of Cu(II) and Ni(II) :

The mixture containing Cu(II) (12.63 mg.) and Ni(II) (12.72 mg.) was taken into a 500 ml. beaker. It was diluted to 200 ml. with distilled water and 10 ml. (0.1 M) of an ammoniacal solution of tartarate and EDTA was added, and the mixture was gently heated for 5 minutes. The pH of the solution was maintained at 5.0-7.0, using acetate buffer. 1% (w/v) reagent (KMDTC) solution was then added with constant stirring. The percipitate was digested at 60-75° for 30 minutes. It was

filtered after an hour in a sintered glass crucible (G-4), washed repeatedly with distilled water, dried at 110-120° for two hours; and weighed as Cu (C₅H₈ONS₂)₂.

The filtrate containing Ni(II) was concentrated, and on cooling 10 ml. of concentrated nitric acid (AR) was added, evaporated to dryness, diluted with 10 ml. of distilled water, and again evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with 150 ml. of distilled water. Any adherent nitric acid was just neutralised with ammonia solution (1 : 1). The 1% (w/v) reagent solution was then added, the yellowish green precipitate obtained was digested at 60-70° for 30 minutes. It was washed with distilled water, dried at 110-120° for two hours, and weighed as Ni(C₅H₈ONS₂)₂.

Copper could be determined with an accuracy of ±0.16 per cent; the accuracy for nickel was ±0.5 per cent.

Results and Discussion :

Properties and composition of the Complex : The copper (II) complex is insoluble in ethanol, acetone, benzene, nitrobenzene, ether, ethylacetate, isopropyl alcohol and dioxane. It is partially soluble in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride, and quite soluble in pyridine and aniline. The copper complex was heated at different temperatures in the oven to a constant weight. It was observed that the complex was stable in between 100°-175° ± 1°. After 175° it starts to decompose slowly.

Digestion of the complex above 85°C yielded low results.

The presence of Ag(I), Pb(II) and Bi(III) interfere in the determination of copper(II).

Structure of the complex :

Based on the elemental analysis and conductometric titrations, the Cu-complex is given the following structure :

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